

MONITORING AND ASSESSMENT OF DESERTIFICATION CHANGE STATUS IN DRYLAND USING GEO-SPATIAL DATA: A CASE STUDY OF JODHPUR DISTRICT, RAJASTHAN

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Abstract

Identification and assessment of source contributions of the land degradation process are critical to ease the effect of desertification. Land use dynamics and climate change are the primary drivers to shift the ecosystem caused by erosion, transportation, and deposition, thus shaping the face of the landscape, especially in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid areas. Sand and dust storm generated through the aeolian process has become a serious threat to the human health, infrastructure, ecosystem functions, and services. Remote sensing and GIS play important role in mapping and monitoring the land undergoing the process of desertification. The objective of the present paper is to assess the change in status of desertification in Jodhpur District, Rajasthan using satellite data for past 24 years in the period of 1992-93 to 2016-17. The desertification status map has been prepared using multi-season Landsat data at 1:50000 scale. The desertification process was significantly noticed in scrubland vegetation degradation as 64% of area has decreased due to anthropogenic activities. The results reveal that undergoing process has modified the study area leading to the betterment of the land due to human-induced efforts while land degradation is concentrated in the north and southwestern part of the district.

Keywords - Aeolian process, Dust storms, Remote Sensing, Desertification, Land degradation

1.0 Introduction

Desertification is one of the greatest environmental problems engrossed by 70% of dryland and one-quarter of the total land in the world¹. It has been identified that every year there is a loss of 200,000 km² of productive land because of desertification due to various causes². The process of desertification includes various physical (wind erosion, water erosion, waterlogging, quarrying of mines, mass wasting), chemical (salinization, acidification), and biological means (declined biodiversity and vegetal degradation)^{3,6}. Due to these factors, desertification has led loss of soil resources in terms of nutrient, structure, and water holding capacity or vegetation composition from grassland to shrubland³⁻⁶. As per UNCCD, land degradation in dryland is called desertification which occurs in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid areas having an evapotranspiration ratio of 0.05-0.65 which is also called as aridity index¹. Sand is formed by erosion, transport, and deposition of weathered material from parent material by the winds in an arid atmosphere which may originate from unconsolidated sediments⁷. The desertic zone of India in Rajasthan has vast sand deposits. This land has abundant sand and silt-sized sediment which are exposed due to wind erosion above the threshold velocity for aeolian transport^{8,9}. The continuous deposition of this material forms sand dunes which have peculiar characteristics depending on the intensity and direction of the wind¹⁰. Thus, understanding the scale and nature of such systems with their reaction to climate and external forces will be valuable to navigate the draught landscape^{9,11-16}.

Remote sensing and GIS are very important techniques helpful in monitoring the process of desertification. Remote sensing data such as IRS, Landsat TM, ETM, MSS, MODIS, NOAA/AVHRR, and SPOT have been widely used for desertification mapping¹⁷⁻²². There are many indicators such as vegetation biomass, net productivity, and land use/landcover change derived from

NDVI, SAVI, MSAVI, and models like RUE to identify the desertification processes^{23,24}. The vast expansion of desertification in the Qinghai province of China is studied from 1970 to 2015²⁵. The effect of climate change on aeolian processes in Tibet region is studied and found to be expanding from its past studies²⁶. Feng et al. 2018 has confirmed the improvement of aeolian desertification in 15 years in Northern China by using MODIS and Gaofen-1 data. Although the Northern Nile delta of Egypt is found to have degraded land which is confirmed using multi-temporal satellite data by El-Kawy and others²⁷. The land surface temperature is also found to give promising results associated with desertification using Landsat ETM data²⁸. Similar studies are conducted around the globe for the desertification process affecting vegetation and other natural resources^{29-32,35,36}.

The following study assessed the desertification process status and change in Jodhpur district using multi-season satellite data during 1992-93 to 2016-17.

2.0 Study area

The study area, Jodhpur district falls in the centre of Rajasthan and lies between 25°51' and 27°37' N latitude and 71°48' and 73°52' E longitude covering an area of 22,850 km² (Fig.1). The district has an arid to a semi-arid type of climate. The mean annual rainfall of the district is 374 mm with maximum rainy days are limited to 15 in a year³³. Almost 80% of the total annual rainfall is received during the southwest monsoon, which enters the district in the first week of July and withdraws in the mid of September. Drought analysis based on agriculture criteria indicates that the district is prone to mild droughts. The occurrence of a severe and very severe type of drought is very rare. As the district lies in the desert area, extremes of heat in summer and cold in winter are the characteristic of the desert. The atmosphere is generally dry except during the monsoon period. Humidity is the highest in August with mean daily relative humidity at 81%. The annual maximum potential evapotranspiration in the district is quite high and is highest (264.7 mm) in May and lowest (76.5 mm) in December. The district has an ample amount of mineral wealth like construction sand, sandstone, Chhitar stone, and brownstone. The district has rich sources of white clay for gluing between stones and about 156 quarries are present for limestone³³.

Fig. 1 Study area Map of Jodhpur District

3.0 Methodology

The detailed methodology is given in the flow chart as shown in Fig 2. Multi-date satellite data of Landsat-5 TM (1992-93) and Landsat-8 OLI/TIRS (2016-17) is used to prepare desertification status maps for monitoring desertification processes in Jodhpur district, Rajasthan through on-screen analysis using visual interpretation keys. Desertification status maps of 1993 and 2017 was prepared and used to assess the change in the area under various processes of desertification as well as degree of severity such as slight, moderate, and severe. Ground truth data is collected from the selected onsite sampling locations. The final desertification map is prepared based on the standardized classification system and interpretation keys^{34,36}.

3.1 Toposheets

The topographic maps or toposheets are kind of maps which provides quantitative measures on a large scale. It represents various features, depending on several methods. The most used method is contour lines, by connecting the places of equal elevation. These maps shows both natural as well as artificial features for ancillary information. It is basically based on observations in a systematic manner for common specifications like coordinate systems, geodetic datum, the map projections, and ellipsoid in combination with cartographic symbols. Official topography includes a referencing system with national grids. The maps show a detailed account of the terrain and landforms of the ground, tree canopy cover, lakes, rivers and other drainage systems, roads, railways and other means of transportation, administrative areas, populated areas and other man-made features. The features of the map are characterized by symbols and signs. These symbols are marked on the corner of the map explaining each feature separately.

Fig. 2 Flow chart of Methodology

4.0 Results and Discussion

Desertification status and change map of Jodhpur district is prepared at 1:50000 scale using multi-date satellite data for the years 1993 and 2017 (fig.3a,b,c) which is further supported by ancillary data. The maps show the spatial distribution and temporal variation in the area and severity of the desertification processes. The analysis of satellite data shows that desertification is widespread in the Jodhpur district of Rajasthan. The table shows seven desertification types/classes found to exist in the study area. The area under desertification during 1993 is 10237 km² (44%) and is decreased to 9022.1 km² (39.4%) in 2017 as shown in Table 1. The desertification status maps show that area under various desertification processes varies considerably. The area under aeolian process is reduced to 6900 km² in 2017 from 7522 km² since 1993. Similarly, area under scrubland vegetal degradation is 1225 km² (5.35%) which is declined 439 km² in 2017. Area under water erosion is reduced from 730 km² in 1993 to 627 km² in 2017. Similarly, area under manmade activities like quarrying, settlement, and installed solar panels have increased to 332.8 km² in 2017 as compared to 1993 which was 128 km². The aeolian degradation is primarily caused by the movement of sand particles and soil around the study area. Aeolian deposits are concentrated to the north, south, and south-western part of the district towards the Thar desert. Various desertification processes (wind erosion, water erosion, vegetal degradation, and sand dunes) as revealed by satellite images and corresponding field photographs are shown in Figs. 4, 5, and 6.

Table 1. Category and area of desertification

Desertification and Land Degradation (DLD) Status Matrix for Jodhpur District			
S.No.	DLD Classes	Area_1993(km²)	Area_2017 (km²)
1	Scrub Land Vegetation Degradation	1225.55 (5.35%)	439.32 (1.92%)
2	Forest Vegetation Degradation	61.97 (0.27%)	65.06 (0.28%)
3	Water Erosion	730.03 (3.19%)	627.69 (2.74%)
4	Aeolian Process	7522.85 (32.88%)	6900.31 (30.17%)
5	Salinity Alkalinity	128.19 (0.56%)	209.89 (0.92%)
6	Man Made	128.11 (0.56%)	332.88 (1.46%)
7	Barren/Rocky	337.06 (1.47%)	344.75 (1.51%)
8	Lake/Reservoir/Tank	103.96 (0.45%)	102.24 (0.45%)
9	NAD	12635.08 (55.24%)	13850.47 (60.55%)
	Total Degraded land	10237	9022
Total		22872.80	22872.61

Fig. 3 Desertification status map for jodhpur district of 1993 (a) and 2017 (b) with DLD change (c)

Fig. 4 Satellite Images and field photographs showing Quarrying and wind erosion processes**Fig. 6** Satellite images and field photographs showing salinity/alkalinity and sand dunes

4.2 Change matrix of land DLD classes and desertification severity

Table 3 explains the change matrix of land degradation classes for the study period from 1993 to 2017. During this period scrub land vegetation degradation class has decreased to 439.3 km² from 1225.5 km² which has contributed to 126 km² in water erosion, 211.6 km² to aeolian activity, 66 km² to salinity/alkalinity, 44.4 km² to manmade activities and with maximum area (470.79 km²) under no apparent degradation (NAD). The scrub land has been used for cultivation and practiced for manmade activities like installation of solar panels. The change matrix of the land under the aeolian process has got converted to no apparent degradation (NAD) class as 2518.74 km² came under this class because of land reclamation for agriculture purpose and sand dunes stabilization through vegetation plantations. Manmade activities have increased from 128 km² to 332.3 km² which has come from NAD and scrubland vegetation degradation since increment in settlement, solar panels, salt pans have occupied by the anthropogenic activities. Water erosion has decreased from 730 km² to 627 km² due to its change to 15.5 km² in aeolian activity, 20.1 km² to barren/rocky and 13.7 km² to manmade and 264.66 km² in NAD because of government policies and programmes for development of rainwater harvesting (Table 2). While no significant change was observed in forest vegetal degradation, salinity/alkalinity, barren rocky and lake/reservoir/tank. NAD area has increased from 12930.4 km² to 13850.6 km² of the area which has increased to 920 km² in 2017. Land

transformation occurred in terms of reversal of DLD classes, as wind-driven activities are less as compared to man-made and salinity alkalinity in the area. The comparison between the years 1993 and 2017 shows the improvement of land through sustainable management practices, and such reclaimed land has been put to agriculture use and other purposes.

The severity index has been prepared and classified as low, moderate, and severe according to their level of severity as given in table 3. The severity index of different DLD classes is explained through the visual interpretation and ground truthing. The severity wise class explains that slight degradation was noticed as 18.85% has increased to 18.98% since 1993. Likewise moderate severity has decreased to 4.62% from 6.88% and the severe class has decreased to 12.8% from 16.64% in 24 years. The details of severity classes based on the land degradation process from the year 1993 to 2017 are mentioned below (Table 3).

Table 2 Change Matrix of Desertification during 1993-2017

CHANGE MATRIX FOR JODHPUR DISTRICT (RAJASTAN) 1993-2017										
DLD CLASS 1993/2017	Scrub Land Vegetation Degradation	Forest Vegetation Degradation	Water Erosion	Aeolian Activity	Salinity / Alkalinity	Barren /Rocky	Lake /Reservoir /Tank	Man Made	NAD	Total
Scrub Land Vegetation Degradation	305.29	0.00	126.16	211.59	66.50	0.06	1.06	44.11	470.79	1225.55
Forest Vegetation Degradation	0.23	56.12	0.00	1.03	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.44	3.92	61.97
Water Erosion	0.19	0.00	415.34	15.49	0.00	20.12	0.51	13.72	264.66	730.03
Aeolian Activity	34.72	0.24	11.54	4631.89	15.78	0.52	0.47	13.65	2518.74	7227.53
Salinity/Alkalinity	0.74	0.00	0.00	32.61	75.65	0.00	0.05	0.00	19.14	128.19
Barren/Rocky	0.00	0.00	2.25	0.73	0.00	318.61	0.23	6.51	8.72	337.06
Lake/Reservoir/Tank	0.21	0.00	0.18	0.78	0.05	0.12	96.78	0.26	5.58	103.96
Man Made	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.42	0.00	0.05	0.03	120.86	6.72	128.11
NAD	97.96	8.67	72.22	2005.77	51.68	5.28	3.12	133.34	1055.236	1293.040
Total	439.33	65.06	627.69	6900.31	209.89	344.75	102.24	332.88	1385.064	2287.280

Table 3 Area statistics of Land degradation Severity classes

Severity Wise Land Degradation Change Status 1993 - 2017				
Land Degradation Class Severity	Area (Sq.km)- 1993	Area (%)	Area (Sq.km)- 2017	Area (%)
Slight	4311.81	18.85	4340.19	18.98
Moderate	1572.94	6.88	1057.08	4.62
Severe	3805.02	16.64	2926.78	12.80
NAD	12635.08	55.24	13850.47	60.55
Barren/Rocky	337.06	1.47	344.75	1.51
Lake/Reservoir/Tank	103.96	0.45	102.24	0.45

Settlement	106.13	0.46	251.08	1.10
	22872	100.00	22872.59	100.00

5.0 Conclusion

Geospatial tool and techniques are important for the analysis of long term changes of desertification status. The analysis of satellite data shows that desertification is widespread in the Jodhpur district of Rajasthan. Seven types of desertification processes have been found to occur with varying severity levels in the Jodhpur district. The area under desertification during 1993 is 10237 km² (44% of geographic area of the district) and is decreased to 9022.1 km² (39.4%) in 2017. The desertification status maps show that area under various desertification processes varies considerably. The area under aeolian process is 32.88% in 1993 which is reduced to 30.17% during 2017. Similarly, area under scrubland vegetal degradation is decreased from 5.35% and in 2017 to 1.92%. Area under water erosion is reduced from 3.19% in 1993 to 2.74% in 2017. However, area under manmade activities like quarrying, settlement, and solar panels installation has increased to 1.46% in 2017 from 0.56% in 1993. Through the combating plan and action by government and local body, the improvement in the land was noticed as the result shows 5% area has improved since 1993 by reclaiming for agriculture, sand dune bunding, tree plantation and water harvesting techniques. The study benefits the livelihood of local community and environment sustainability.

Declaration- We the undersigned declare that this manuscript is original, has not been published before and is not currently being considered for publication elsewhere. We understand that the Corresponding Author is the sole contact for the Editorial process. She is responsible for communicating with the other authors about progress, submissions of revisions, and final approval of proofs.

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